

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of commonly used mouse model of CAA, including associated mutations, CAA onset, and key features (Note: This is not an exhaustive list)

Table 2: Dysregulation status of keys endothelial tight and adherens junctions' genes.

Table 3: GSEA results using a custom gene list: endothelial genes from Bryant et al. 2023[1] and genes positively or negatively correlated with CAA from Sun et al. 2023[2].

Table 4: Dysregulation status of chromosome 21 genes that could have an impact on the endothelial functions.

List of supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: Summary of articles identified through a systematic review investigating cerebrovascular risk associated with cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) in Down syndrome (DS). The table includes the number of cases analyzed in each study or, when applicable, the model system employed. *DS was mentioned as similar to AD but no actual cases were used in the paper.

Supplementary Table 2: Number of PubMed records retrieved for each keyword combination with "Down Syndrome" as the primary term. The literature search was conducted up to December 2024. Keywords were selected to cover vascular, cellular, and pathological features relevant to cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) in Down syndrome. See Supplementary Figure 1 for the complete search workflow.

Supplementary Table 3: List of RNA-seq samples with associated batch information, differentiation identifiers, and passage numbers.

Supplementary Table 4: List of Chr21 genes up regulated in DSI and not dysregulated in APPdup in Fig.3-4C.

Supplementary Table 5: Full GSEA results for the DSI vs DSI isogenic comparison. All tested gene sets are included.

Supplementary Table 6: Full GSEA results for the APPdup vs APPdup isogenic comparison. All tested gene sets are included.

Supplementary Table 7: GSEA results for each module identified by WGCNA on the DSI vs DSI isogenic and independent control samples.

Supplementary Table 8: GSEA results for each module identified by WGCNA on the APPdup vs APPdup isogenic samples.

Supplementary Table 9: Full GSEA results for the APPdup2 vs APPdup2 isogenic comparison. All tested gene sets are included.

Supplementary Table 10: List of expressed genes, their dysregulation status and associated values for DS1 vs DS1 isogenic (sheet1) and APPdup vs APPdup isogenic (sheet2).

Supplementary Table 11: Expression matrix in cpm of all genes across all samples.

Bibliography

1. Bryant A, Li Z, Jayakumar R, Serrano-Pozo A, Woost B, Hu M, et al. Endothelial Cells are Heterogeneous in Different Brain Regions and are Dramatically Altered in Alzheimer's Disease [Internet]. bioRxiv; 2023 [cited 2023 Aug 29]. p. 2023.02.16.528825. Available from: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.02.16.528825v1>
2. Sun N. Single-nucleus multiregion transcriptomic analysis of brain vasculature in Alzheimer's disease. Nat Neurosci. 2023;26.